

ORGANIZATION AND PLANNING OF MARKETING RESEARCH PROCESSES IN THE ENTERPRISE

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Abstract. *In this article, receiving, processing, production of cotton products and their sale, wholesale and retail trade - sales, mediation; engaged in supply activities, production of consumer goods and paid services to the population were considered.*

Keywords: *marketing research, enterprise, society, cotton, supply, service, production.*

INTRODUCTION. Our Uzbekistan is a land of real peasants with its ancient school of agriculture and traditions, capable of extracting wealth from the soil. According to ancient sources, cotton cultivation came to us in 2000 BC, and the field of its processing appeared almost at the same time.

Cotton processing - cleaning, weeding, fiber and fluff extraction started at the same time as cotton planting, and over the centuries, approximately until the end of the 19th century - the beginning of the 20th century, it was carried out in the simplest way, i.e. chigirig, charkh, devcharkh, yig, savag. It was done with simple tools like 'ich.

The main goal of Tsarist Russia in colonizing Central Asia was to occupy areas suitable for cotton cultivation and thereby provide its textile enterprises with this valuable raw material. Merchants and industrialists of Tsarist Russia were initially limited to buying ginned cotton from the markets, and later, in order to develop the industry, they imported fast-growing medium-fiber cotton varieties from Mexico to the formation of large companies engaged in cotton production, the construction of cotton gins caused.

The first steam-powered cotton ginning factory in Turkestan was built in Tashkent in 1874. After a few years, such factories began to operate in Andijan, Kattakorgan, Samarkand, Margilon, Kokan and Namangan. In these enterprises, almost all work was done by hand.

Large companies are engaged in buying the cultivated cotton crop from farmers, processing it in factories and paying for the fiber. and he would hand over the products he grew only to the weigher who gave them a stamp, and the weighers would buy three-fourths of the cotton grown in Turkestan. Thus, Uzbek peasants became dependent on the capital of usurious merchants of Russia.

In 1913, cotton was planted on an area of 424.6 thousand hectares in Turkestan, and there were 208 low-power cotton factories in three agricultural regions: Fergana, Syrdarya, and Samarkand, where more than 8,000 workers worked.

By 1918, during the nationalization of the cotton industry, 120 out of 296 cotton gins were partially mechanized. The rest are based on manual labor. Three years later, for various reasons, only 16 cotton mills remained. The equipment of the closed factories was looted.

At that time, there was no machine-building plant in Turkestan that produced equipment for cotton processing enterprises. Only in 1927, when the first machine-building plant was put into operation in Tashkent, the cotton fields expanded somewhat. In those years, cotton was planted on 543.2 thousand hectares in Uzbekistan, and the yield was 10.52 centners per hectare. To process

this crop in a timely manner, high-capacity cotton mills were needed, and by 1928, the number of cotton gins in Central Asia had reached 62.

In 1940, fiber production in Uzbekistan reached 500,000 tons, but during the Second World War, the yield per hectare decreased significantly, that is, in 1943, this indicator did not exceed 8 centners. In 1958, the capacity of cotton ginning plants was able to process 3.5 million tons of cotton. By 1980, the actual amount of fiber produced was 1,745,3 thousand tons, and the number of gins was 729.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. It can be seen that the system of cotton cultivation and processing in our country has come a long way. But only after the independence of Uzbekistan, the period of real development began in the cotton industry, as in all other sectors.

One of the important indicators for the joint stock company "Juma Pafta Pashto" is the distribution of shares. Shares and shareholders have a great influence on the operation of the enterprise. If there are foreign investors among the shareholders, it will have a positive effect on the activity and modern development of the enterprise. The following table shows the distribution of shares of "Juma cotton cleaning" JSC.

Society is a commercial organization, the main purpose of which is to make a profit from financial and economic activities.

To achieve its main goal, the society performs the following types of activities and services:

- purchase, storage, processing of cotton raw materials in the prescribed manner, production of high-quality cotton products resistant to competition in the world market, thereby increasing the economic efficiency of the society and obtaining profit;

- conclusion of contractual agreements with cotton-growing agricultural enterprises and farms regarding the purchase and processing of cotton raw materials;

- purchase of raw cotton in accordance with the contractual agreements and timely processing in accordance with the specified plans and tasks, delivery of manufactured cotton products to consumers;

- providing cotton-growing farms with high-quality seeds of selection varieties that are popular in the world cotton market;

- bookkeeping with cotton-growing agricultural enterprises and farms in accordance with the contractual agreements concluded on the purposeful use of funds, the purchase and processing of cotton raw materials;

- ensuring the reliability of data on the purchase of raw cotton, the production of cotton fiber and other cotton products, their shipment to consumers, and accounting and reporting on the balance of these products, the volume of cotton production, and its sale to consumers of the republic;

- development of the market mechanism for the production of consumer goods;

- technical equipment of society, modernization, attraction of foreign investments, creation of conditions for development of society;

- stabilization of the economic and financial situation of the society, effective use of the investment portfolio, creation of comfortable, modern conditions for the labor team, strengthening of their economic interests;

- Making a worthy contribution to the development of the cotton processing industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

- making effective investments for economic activity in the society based on the agreement with the investors in the prescribed manner;

- Acquisition, sale, lease, rental of property, real estate, intellectual property in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

- organization of wholesale and retail trade of produced consumer goods;

- production and sale of agricultural, including livestock products.

The society has the right to carry out other types of activities not prohibited by the normative legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Activities that require a special permit (license) are carried out by the society after obtaining a license in accordance with the procedure established by law.

In order to achieve the goals set forth in this Charter, the company may carry out investment and other types of activities not prohibited by the normative legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The society can carry out other types of activities specified in the legislation in the prescribed manner.

"The main goal of the society's activity is to obtain income on legal grounds, taking into account the interests of the members of the society, and the following are its main tasks:

- to ensure the effective functioning of society;

- not to harm the interests of society members;

- development of mechanisms, strengthening the economic interest of agricultural and cotton ginning enterprises in the production of high-quality cotton products that are resistant to competition in the world market;

- conclusion of contractual agreements with cotton-growing agricultural enterprises and farms for the purchase and processing of cotton raw materials with the participation of service banks;

- procurement and processing of cotton raw materials and delivery of cotton products for export and domestic market in accordance with the contractual agreements;

- organization of high-quality reception, storage and processing of seed cotton raw materials by providing cotton-growing farms with high-quality seeds of selection varieties that are popular in the world cotton market;

- to ensure targeted use of the funds allocated by the regional joint-stock association "Pakhtasanoat", which is the top organization of the system, to make accounts with cotton-growing agricultural enterprises and farms in accordance with the contractual agreements concluded on the purchase and processing of raw cotton;

- information on the purchase of raw cotton, the production of cotton fiber and other cotton products, their shipment to consumers and the balance of these products, the purchase of raw cotton, the volume of production of cotton products, and their sale to consumers of the republic ensuring reliability;

- creating conditions for technical re-equipment, modernization and development of the cotton ginning enterprise.

Based on the tasks assigned to it in paragraph 2.1, the society engages in the following types of activities:

- reception of raw cotton materials, processing, production of cotton products and their sale;
- engage in wholesale and retail trade - sales, mediation;
- engage in supply activities;
- construction, construction-assembly, repair work;
- production and sale of agricultural and livestock products;
- production of consumer goods and provision of paid services to the population;
- Engages in any other activity not prohibited by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

If the company engages in activities required to be carried out by means of a special permit (license) under the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it can be carried out only if the company has a special permit.

Table 1

Technical and economic indicators of "Juma cotton ginning" JSC for 2018-2022

No	Indicators	Unit of measure	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
1.	Refined cotton fiber	tons	57659	61057	69107	51886	53484
2.	Prepared seed seed	tons	6981	7524	7451	8200	8275
3.	Sold cotton fiber	tons	57659	61057	69107	51886	53484
4.	Total revenue received	million soum	4812410	6269069	7047936	7452628	8124934
5.	Expenses incurred	million soum	4594671	5969171	6838391	7288611	7974419
6.	Profit before tax	million soum	217739	299898	209545	164017	150515
7.	Net profit	million soum	769471	760458	934145	813091	852072
8.	Profitability	%	2.0	1.6	1.5	1.2	1.7

Source: "Author's development based on the reports of Juma Cotton Cleaning JSC

As can be seen from this table, "In the last two years, the volume of cotton fiber produced and sold in Juma cotton ginning JSC in 2021-2022 has been decreasing. In 2020, 69,107 tons of cotton fibers were sold, and in 2022, 53,484 tons of cotton fibers were sold. But the volume of prepared seeds is increasing year by year. In 2018, 6,981 tons of seeds were delivered, and in 2022, 8,275 tons of seeds were prepared. During 2018-2022, an average of 7,686 tons of seeds were prepared.

The volume of income and net profit is increasing due to the increase in the volume of prepared seed and changes in the price of cotton fiber. But the profitability of the enterprise is low. In 2018, the profitability of the enterprise was 2.0 percent, in 2021 it was 1.2 percent, and in 2022 it was 1.7 percent.

To increase the profitability of the enterprise, first of all, it is necessary to achieve full loading of the activities of the main production shops. This is one of the most difficult issues to achieve if production capacity is not utilized to the maximum.

"Juma Cotton Cleaning" JSC's first shop A is a cotton fiber production shop. Cotton fiber is produced in this workshop. Cotton fiber is mainly divided into assortments according to the type and packaging size. The composition of cotton fiber produced by JSC "Juma cotton cleaning" consists of high-grade and first-grade raw materials, seed, kunjara and shulukha. Increasing the volume of cotton fiber production, filling the domestic market with local products for the production of textile products, reducing the volume of imports and producing export-oriented products, as well as creating new jobs are among the urgent issues.

"The number of employees in "Juma cotton cleaning" JSC is also increasing to a certain extent from year to year. In particular, in 2018, 1,200 workers worked, and in 2022, 2,100 more workers are working. Labor productivity is also increasing.

The most common method of analyzing enterprise activity is the matrix method. The product profile matrix consists of a two-dimensional grid, which represents the positions of the company's strategy. Three types of matrices are used in the development of a target market expansion strategy:

- Boston Consulting Group (BKG) "growth-share" matrix;
- General Electric company's "industry attractiveness-strengths" matrix;
- Hofer-Lottl's product life cycle matrix.

The BKG, or "growth-share" matrix, consists of four quadrants and is visualized using sales growth and relative market share as axes. A production or commodity type is arranged in the form of circles in a four-quadrant matrix. Their location and positions are determined based on the calculation of the growth rates of the market and the relative market shares of the goods.

We recommend using the model called the BKG matrix in the formation of the product strategy of manufacturing enterprises. To use this method, you must first build the BKG matrix. Two indicators are used to construct the BKG matrix:

- The growth rate of the commodity market or the volume of commodity sales;
 - The relative share of the enterprise in the market compared to the main competitor;
- These indicators are calculated for all types of production and goods.

Table 2

Information on production growth rate and relative market share

Production, types of goods	Growth rate	Relative market share	Share of product volume in sales
First assortment	Y1	N1	C1
Second assortment	Y2	N2	C2
-----	Y3	i	i
Indicator production	Yn	No	Cn

The next stages of creating the BKG matrix are carried out in the following order:

1. The general area of the product strategy is constructed with the help of coordinate axes. In this case, the growth rate of the market is shown on the vertical axis, and the market share of the enterprise is shown on the horizontal axis.

2. On the basis of the data calculated in Table 2, the types of production or goods of the enterprise are determined in the strategy area.

3. The average values of the market growth rate and market share are determined on the coordinate axes. By drawing circular lines from them, the product strategy space is divided into four quadrants and the BKG matrix is created. An overview of the BKG matrix is shown in Figure 5. As a result of the analysis and evaluation of the created matrix, decisions are made regarding the company's production or product strategy. Such decisions can be made for each product type, assortment or nomenclature.

Each of these four quadrants requires different approaches in terms of product financing and product strategy development.

Quadrant I shows the high growth rate of the commodity market and the high relative market share and is called the symbolic stars. It is necessary to develop a strategy to strengthen and strengthen the production of goods located in this quadrant. These goods have a large share in the market and the market is on a growing trend. The production of these goods is one of the main types of enterprise business in the near future. But as the market becomes more and more saturated, the former milk cows will be replaced.

Quadrant II shows a low growth rate of the commodity market and a high relative market share of the commodity. These products generate more revenue than the amount of money required to maintain market share. They are the sources of financial means for the development of diversification or research. That is why they are called milk cows.

Quadrant III shows the low growth rate of the commodity market and the commodity's low relative market share. The chronic continuation of the production of such goods requires large expenditures, the probability of improvement of the situation is very small. Therefore, goods located in this quadrant are conventionally called dogs. Because they need to be fed. The priority commodity strategy in this case is to get these commodities out of production, to mobilize the fixed and working capital associated with these commodities for faster promising innovations.

Quadrant IV shows a high growth rate of the commodity market and a low relative market share. There are opportunities for the development of goods in this group, because the market is expanding. But if these goods are not provided with financial support, they risk becoming "dogs" during their life cycle. Here, the strategy of increasing market share and reinvestment is required.

In order to correctly use the BKG matrix in the development of a brand strategy in the practice of manufacturing enterprises, it is necessary to be able to correctly assess the growth rate of the market and the relative market share of the enterprise. We recommend using no more than the following year's reporting data when estimating market growth.

A logical analysis of the BKG matrix leads to the following conclusion. Using it, the current state of production of goods of the production enterprise is determined. A product strategy is developed based on this situation. A reasonable balance of financial support of the developed strategy is drawn up.

In order to use the BKG matrix to expand the product range of JSC "Juma cotton cleaning", we need to determine the growth rate of the company's product range and the relative share of the market. For this purpose, we will use the tabular data from the analysis of the enterprise's sales activity in the above chapters. In particular - to build the BKG matrix using the data from the table - we create a table. Based on the data in the table, we analyze the average growth rate of the company's sales of 15 types of assortments in 2020-2022. To do this, we find the average three-year arithmetic sales volume of each assortment and, taking the result as a base year, find the growth rate in 2022.

In order to find the relative share of the market, we first determine the most leading competitor of the enterprise for the sale of exactly similar goods, and the share of the leading competitor in the total market capacity of the market for the sale of this product and the total market capacity of the joint-stock company "Juma Pafta Pashka" the share is determined and placed in the table. A company uses what it considers to be the most dominant competitor in the market it operates in to find its relative market share.

Table 3

Information about the goods sold by JSC "Juma cotton ginning" in 2017-2019

No	Types of clothing	2020 year	2021 year	2022 year	Market share, %	
					of the enterprise	Leading competitor
1.	#1 Cotton fiber	10175.0	12180.0	23040.0	1.2	4.8
2.	#2 Cotton fiber	1380.0	4200.0	6480.0	2.3	2.1
3.	#3 Cotton fiber	9180.0	21420.0	33600.0	1.6	3.5
4.	#4 Cotton fiber	25500.0	46800.0	73320.0	1.1	2.9
5.	#5 Cotton fiber	4050.0	11550.0	15840.0	3.8	1.6
6.	#1 Seed seeds	15300.0	23040.0	17280.0	4.2	3.4
7.	#2 Seed seeds	1200.0	2432.0	4320.0	1.2	5.0
8.	#3 Seed seeds	4125.0	7500.0	11700.0	0.8	2.6
9.	#4 Seed seeds	13200.0	21000.0	27720.0	2.7	1.3
10.	#1 Kunjara	13600.0	13950.0	21600.0	0.7	3.2
11.	#2 Kunjara	24960.0	55300.0	81600.0	1.3	5.2
12.	#3 Kunjara	1800.0	4950.0	8040.0	1.6	2.1
13.	#1 Shulukha	29400.0	38650.0	44880.0	3.5	1.6
14.	#2 Shulukha	42120.0	46008.0	46400.0	1.1	6.2
15.	#3 Shulukha	11088.0	12008.0	14440.0	2.3	3.1
	TOTAL	207078	320988	430260		

Based on the data of this table, we analyze the table to construct the BKG matrix. Based on the results of the analysis, we make the following table 4. The main indicators are the growth rate of product sales, i.e. the growth rate of the market, the relative share of the market and the contribution of each assortment to the total sales.

Table 4

Data for building the BKG matrix

K	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
T	2.0	1.6	1.5	1.5	1.5	0.9	1.6	1.5	1.3	0.3	1.5	1.6	1.1	1.0	1.1
			7	1	1	3	3	0	4	7	1	3	9	3	5
B	0.2	1.0	0.4	0.3	2.4	1.2	0.2	0.3	2.0	0.2	0.2	0.7	2.1	0.1	0.7
	5	9	6	8		3	4	1	7	2	5	6	8	7	4
SH	5.4	1.5	7.8	17.	3.7	4.1	1.1	2.7	6.4	5.0	18.	1.9	10.	10.	3.3
E				0							9		4	8	
IS															

Note:

K- indicators;

T-goods growth rate

B - Relative share of the market

U - The share of goods in the total sales volume

Numbers 1-15 are the corresponding numbers of the goods in the table above

We place the BKG matrix in the coordinate plane. For this, we place the relative market share of the enterprise on the abscissa axis, and the growth rate of goods on the ordinate axis.

To construct the BKG matrix of JSC "Juma cotton ginning" products, we determine the average arithmetic of the indicators of the growth rate of the network and the relative share of the market:

Putting the calculated values on the axes of the growth rate of the network and the relative share of the market, we divide the coordinate plane into 4 quadrants and build the BKG matrix. - taking the data in the table as the coordinates of "Growth rate of goods" and "Relative share of the market", the diameter of the circle containing the points corresponding to these coordinates shows the share of this service in the total realization.

In this BKG matrix, the profit from goods number 2 and 5, that is, children's T-shirts and baby sets, is very important. But at the same time, a large amount of financial resources will be needed for further growth. Therefore, the main goal of the company's strategy is to maintain and strengthen leadership. For this, it may be appropriate to improve the goods, reduce the price, increase the advertising activities and wide distribution. However, with the slowdown of network development, "Yulduz" became "Milk cows".

The "product-market" matrix is also widely used in the expansion of the company's product assortment program. The "product-market" matrix focuses on the company's entry into new markets and the adoption of new products. This matrix is formed depending on the company's capabilities, products, markets, competitive situation, consumers and direction of activity. The main thing is that the company develops marketing strategies based on its resources and developing sectors.

This matrix envisages strategy development based on market and product updates. The starting point is the difference between the real and planned development of the enterprise. This means that the company's goal cannot be achieved using the previous strategy. A goal is needed, or it needs to be corrected, or a new strategic path must be sought.

The matrix was proposed by I. Ansoff, an American scientist of Russian origin. He called it the "product-market" rule. An overview of this rule is as follows:

Table 5

"Product-market" matrix

Market Product	There is	new
There is	Deep market penetration	Product processing
new	Market development	Diversification

The matrix consists of four areas, situations arising from the influence of two factors determining the position of the enterprise (growth and market and product changes):

- the enterprise operates with existing (old) products in the existing market;
- the enterprise offers a new product to the existing market;
- the enterprise enters the new market with existing (old) products;
- the enterprise enters a new market with new products.

A company's marketing efforts determine the direction of each strategic quadrant. In particular, the market entry strategy, as a rule, promotes goods with traditional buyers, increases market share, attracts buyers from competitors or new consumers. Based on the matrix, four alternative strategies are used.

Market penetration strategy recommended when the firm is dealing with a sufficiently popular brand in the existing market. It seems that it has been taken over, and the firm has no chance of success. However, it can be found in accelerating the movement of goods, that is, in finding new, more experienced and active distributors, in improving the channels of the movement of goods, in creating a vertical marketing system. Second, aspects that can help the firm are active advertising, sales and various forms of sales promotion, service events and other methods of influencing the consumer. A firm may try to expand its market size by lowering prices to a level acceptable to a large number of consumers. The price elasticity of demand should work.

Product handling strategy. It was recommended when the firm participates in the old, sufficiently saturated market, and makes improvements to the goods that exist among consumers and create a desire in them to replace old goods with new ones, taking into account the effectiveness of moral obsolescence of goods. The appearance of a new high-quality product often creates an additional increase in demand. However, there is a need for active advertising, enhanced brand awareness efforts, such as organizing trade shows, product presentations, and marketing activities that support various sales and promotion methods.

Market development strategy. If the demand for the old product was sufficient to sell the goods and get the planned profit, it will be effective at the expense of identifying new market segments. The enterprise forms a market advantage from the position of attracting more policy in relation to potential consumers and at the same time to the main competitors. Here, first of all, a certain process is studied on the basis of competitive analysis, and the need arises to evaluate the competitive advantage of the enterprise, both its own and competitors in the market.

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